

A Comparative Study on Approaches upon Ethical Issues in Digital Transformation: Estonia and Singapore

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Abstract

The paper explores, in a comparative way, the strategies adopted by Estonia and Singapore in addressing ethical challenges within the realm of digital transformation. Estonia and Singapore have demonstrated strong commitments to ethical digital governance through the establishment of robust legal frameworks and regulatory bodies aimed at protecting privacy and promoting responsible digital practices. While Estonia's approach emphasizes transparency and government-led initiatives, Singapore's strategy revolves around compliance, collaboration with industries, and addressing the societal implications of automation. This paper highlights the importance of considering ethical issues in digital transformation and provides suggestions for policymakers and practitioners on how to approach ethical issues in digital transformation. Recommendations for governments include the establishment of strict data protection laws, investment in digital literacy programs, promotion of transparency, fostering international collaboration, and achieving a delicate balance between innovation and ethics. The global community must prioritize ethical considerations to ensure a positive societal impact and foster inclusive progress in the digital age.

Keywords: *digital transformation, ethics, privacy, governance, collaboration, compliance.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The global landscape is changing rapidly due to the influence of digital transformation. This shift has not only brought us efficient ways of doing things and better access to information but has also raised important questions about the impact of these changes. As technology advances, concerns about privacy, biases, and accountability have emerged. These are complex issues that require careful consideration and ethical decision-making. This paper focuses on exploring how two countries, Estonia and Singapore, are dealing with these ethical challenges in the realm of digital transformation. By studying their approaches, we can gain valuable insights into the different paths nations take to address ethical concerns in the digital age. Estonia and Singapore are chosen as case studies because they provide distinct examples of how countries navigate the intricate landscape of ethical digital governance.

Estonia's trailblazing initiatives in digital governance have positioned it as a pioneer in the field. The nation has implemented various digital solutions, from e-governance to e-residency programs, with the aim of making services more accessible and efficient for its citizens. Singapore, on the other hand, has become a global hub for technology and innovation, attracting businesses and talent from around the world. Both countries showcase unique

approaches to integrating technology into their societies, but they also grapple with ethical considerations inherent in these advancements. Through this comparative exploration, we seek not only to analyze the strategies of Estonia and Singapore but also to draw connections to the broader global conversation on ethical digital transformation. The purpose is to cultivate a nuanced comprehension of ethical principles and legal frameworks essential for fostering effective governance practices and gain comprehensive insights from digital transformation successful countries.

Additionally, this paper serves as a journey through the ethical landscapes of Estonia and Singapore, offering a nuanced perspective on their responses to the challenges posed by digital transformation.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Why Ethics are Important in Digital Transformation?

Ethics play a crucial role in digital transformation, safeguarding individuals' rights, respecting privacy, and fostering trust among stakeholders. They promote fairness and equity by addressing biases and minimizing disparities. Ethical frameworks protect against security and privacy risks, ensuring technology is used responsibly. Ethics also promote innovation aligned with societal values and regulatory requirements, promoting long-term sustainability. Countries like Estonia and Singapore demonstrate how ethical considerations are integrated into their digital strategies, highlighting the importance of ethics in navigating digital transformation complexities.

2.2 Ethical Issues in Digital Transformation

Our journey into the digital era brings about ethical concerns that need attention, as responsible governance becomes crucial. Here are some significant ethical challenges we might encounter:

Privacy Concerns in the Digital Age: The rise of social media and online platforms means people are sharing a lot of personal information. Companies and governments can collect and use this information without our clear agreement. This creates a big privacy issue with technology, and we need to figure out how to protect personal privacy in this digital world.

Spreading Misinformation on the Internet: The internet is like a super-fast messenger, but sometimes the information shared might not be true. Imagine if someone makes up stories or shares the wrong videos. That can lead to problems in society. Solving this issue means finding ways to stop false information and making sure what we see online is trustworthy.

Digital Divide and Unequal Access: Not everyone has the same access to digital resources. Some people miss out on education, jobs, and being part of the community because of the digital divide. In many developing countries, some regions don't have internet or tech access, making things harder for them. Ethically, we need to make sure everyone has fair access to digital opportunities.

Unethical Use of AI-generated Content: The strength of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is incredible. Some people can use AI unethically to create fake photos and videos, and others might share and distribute them repeatedly. This is a significant ethical issue because of AI, and it's considered one of the top risks in 2024, according to a report by the Eurasia Group.

Job Displacement and Skills Gap: The use of AI and technology might lead to some people losing their jobs. At the same time, there's a growing gap between the skills needed for tech jobs and the talent available. Ethical responses to these challenges involve making sure people have the right skills for the changing job market and creating policies that consider the impact of technology on employment.

2.3 Ways to manage ethical issues

There are some ways to handle ethical issues for organizations;

Identify Ethical Issues: Take the time to recognize any ethical challenges that might arise within the organization. This involves being aware of potential risks and understanding how they might impact the workplace.

Develop Ethical Guidelines: Create clear and easy-to-follow rules that guide everyone in the organization on how to make ethical decisions. These guidelines serve as a roadmap for ensuring that actions align with ethical principles.

Create an Ethical Culture: Foster an environment where ethical behavior is not just encouraged but becomes a part of everyday work. This involves promoting honesty, fairness, and responsibility in all aspects of the organization's activities.

On the other hand, Government can handle ethical issues using the following ways.

Regulatory Frameworks: Set up and enforce rules and regulations that guide ethical behavior in the digital realm. This includes creating laws and policies that set clear expectations for individuals and organizations, ensuring accountability.

Collaborative Initiatives: Work together with private sectors and other organizations to address ethical challenges collectively. Collaborative efforts enhance the effectiveness of ethical practices and encourage a united approach.

Public Awareness Campaigns: Inform the public about the importance of ethical behavior through campaigns. These campaigns aim to raise awareness, ensuring that people understand the significance of ethical conduct in the digital age.

Implementing these straightforward strategies not only helps organizations and governments ethical issues effectively but also contributes to creating a digital environment that prioritizes responsibility, transparency, and ethical conduct.

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology is based on the comparison of two countries that have either introduced or are considering approaches upon ethical issues in digital transformation: Estonia and Singapore. This study compares approaches upon ethical issues like (a) Strategies and regulation and (b) additional initiatives in two countries, Estonia and Singapore.

3.1 Approaches upon Ethical Issues: Estonia

Estonia is pioneer in digital transformation and a leading adopter of emerging technologies like Block chain, with a strong focus on transparency, accountability, and individual rights. And this country is the only country in the world to offer e-residency and the first country to adopt online voting. The Estonian government has developed a number of initiatives to promote ethical digital governance.

(a) **Strategies and Regulation:** The following strategies and regulations are made by Estonia Government as;

Personal Data Protection Act: Estonia has rules called the Personal Data Protection Act to keep personal information safe. This Act provides for 1) standards for implementation of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council; 2) standards for transposition of Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA (OJ L 119, 04.05.2016, pp. 89-131); 3) procedure for exercise of state supervision over compliance with the requirements for the processing of personal data; 4) liability for the violation of the requirements for processing of personal data. And, this includes important principles like being legality and fairness, purposefulness, quality, accuracy, retention and security for processing of the data. It also makes sure data can be used for specific grounds like journalism, academics, and law enforcement, with a special agency called the Estonian Data Protection Inspectorate making sure everyone follows the rules.

e-Identity: In Estonia, people can do lots of things online without giving away their info. Every Estonian has a digital identity that is issued by the state, regardless of where they live. This e-ID, or electronic identity system, has been the backbone of the nation's e-state for more than 20 years. Any citizen's everyday transactions in the public and private sectors involve e-ID and the ecosystem that supports it. Estonians can utilize their e-Identity through state-issued ID-cards, Mobile-ID on smartphones. Estonia offers e-Residency program since 2014, allowing anyone with a digital identity to access its diverse digital services, regardless of citizenship or location. Estonia uses its eID for secure data transfers, electronic signatures, and electronic identity. eID enables secure and efficient use of various state and private sector e-services. Estonia's government-backed eID offers great security and reliability for both users and e-service providers. The government keeps a record of these digital identities to make sure things are done right and no one misuses information.

e-Governance Academy: The e-Governance Academy (eGA) is a leading institution dedicated to enhancing society's prosperity and openness through digital transformation. Since 2002, eGA has collaborated with over 290

organizations in 143 countries to establish successful digital societies, enhancing citizens' lives, strengthening economies, and promoting transparent, democratic, and effective public administrations. The academy conducts training programs, workshops, and conferences to help governments, policymakers, and professionals from around the world understand and implement effective e-governance strategies and share best practice. It covers topics such as digital identity, data protection, cybersecurity, e-services, and the overall digital transformation of governance. The core areas of digital transformation are covered by e-GA services, which offer helpful support to public sector and civil society organizations at every step of their digital initiatives. The latest ISO 9001:2015 quality standard is certified for e-GA.

Estonia's way of doing things not only makes them a digital champ but also shows how to be responsible and open in the digital world.

(b) Additional Initiatives: The following initiatives are being made by Estonia Government as;

National AI Strategy: Estonia has a plan, called the national AI strategy, with four pillars: boosting AI in the government, AI in economy, skills along with research and development, and the legal environment. Estonia is implementing a government-as-platform strategy as part of its national AI plan to enhance AI adoption in the public sector and the economy. The planned activities involve a public e-course to increase AI awareness and the creation of sandboxes for testing public sector AI applications. The private sector will be able to create machine learning-based solutions by using designated innovation and development funding.

Public Awareness Campaigns: The Estonian government regularly conducts public awareness campaigns to educate citizens about their rights and responsibilities. So, they run campaigns to tell the public about it. They also promote awareness via e-estonia.com and e-Estonia YouTube channel. This way, people understand how their data is used, and they can make informed decisions.

Citizen Participation in Policy Development: Estonia actively involves citizens in the development of digital governance policies. This participatory approach ensures that policies reflect the needs and concerns of the public and are implemented in an ethical and responsible manner.

Estonian Open Data Portal: Estonia has established a comprehensive open data platform that provides public access to government data sets. Anyone can access licensed data shared by the private and third sectors as well as uncontrolled public sector data through the open data portal. Reusing data for non-commercial as well as commercial objectives is permitted by licenses granted by information owners.

Estonia's additional initiatives show that they not only care about using technology but also about doing it in a way that benefits everyone and keeps things fair and open.

3.2 Approaches upon Ethical Issues: Singapore

Singapore is another country that is at the forefront of digital transformation and has a forward-looking approach to compliance and regulation in digital transformation. Singapore's Smart Nation initiative is a comprehensive effort to leverage technology and data to improve the quality of life for its citizens. The government is committed to ethical and responsible digital practices, combining legal frameworks, governance guidelines, and proactive initiatives.

(a) **Strategies and Regulations:** The following strategies and regulations are made by Singapore Government as;

Personal Data Protection Act (PDPA): The Personal Data Protection Act (PDPA) provides a baseline standard of protection for personal data in Singapore. This act governs the collection, use, and disclosure of individuals' personal data by organizations in a manner that recognizes both the right of individuals to protect their personal data, and the need of organizations to collect, use, and disclose personal data for purposes that a reasonable person would consider appropriate in the circumstances. To achieve full compliance with the Singapore privacy law, there are eleven data protection obligations. These are Accountability, Consent, Purpose Limitation, Notification, Access and Correction, Accuracy, Protection, Retention Limitation, Transfer Limitation, Data breach Notification and Data Portability. Organizations are required to comply with the various data protection obligations. Personal data kept in both non-electronic and electronic formats is covered under the PDPA.

Personal Data Protection Commission (PDPC): The PDPC oversees and enforces the Personal Data Protection Act. Its responsibilities include setting guidelines, enforcing compliance, promoting awareness about data protection, and providing advisory services to organizations. The goal is to make sure personal data is handled responsibly and that people's privacy rights are respected.

Model AI Governance Framework: The Model Framework offers comprehensive guidance for private sector organizations to tackle ethical and governance concerns when implementing AI solutions. The principles focus on being accountable, accurate, transparent, fair, and considering human well-being. This Framework aims to enhance public understanding and trust in AI systems by promoting data accountability, transparency, and open communication practices. The Model Framework is primarily focused on four broad areas such as internal governance structures and measures, determining the level of human involvement in AI-augmented decision-making, Operations management and Stakeholder interaction and communication.

(b) **Additional Initiatives:** The following strategies and regulations are being made by Singapore Government as;

National AI Strategy: Singapore's National AI Strategy, published in 2019, aims to deepen the use of AI to transform the economy. The strategy includes national AI projects in Education, Healthcare, and Safety & Security, as well as investments in enablers. AI presents both opportunities and risks, but must be managed responsibly to avoid cyber threats and misinformation. The Singapore Government's updated NAIS 2.0 focuses on excellence and empowerment, aiming to develop AI peaks for global issues like population health and climate change. The strategy will focus on three systems, working through 10 enablers.

Public Awareness Campaigns: Singapore runs campaigns to make sure people know about the digital world. For example, Digital Readiness program to improve Digital Access, Digital Literacy and Digital Participation and Skills Future Initiatives help raise awareness and understanding of technology, ensuring that everyone is informed about the benefits and potential risks. They also promote awareness via websites and YouTube channel such as Skills Future Singapore, MCI Singapore, etc.

National Digital Identity: The National Digital Identity Initiative (NDI) was created to give individuals more security and convenience while interacting with the public and private sectors online. Singpass, Myinfo, and Myinfo Business have been combined under the NDI to offer enhanced transaction security and user-friendliness. It enhances efficiency by facilitating secure, consent-based verification for the private sector. Singaporean citizens utilize Singpass, a dependable digital identity, for both online and offline access to public and commercial sector services. It adds an extra layer of security by using two-factor authentication, which includes a username/password and a one-time password (OTP).

Collaborative Initiatives: Singapore is known for its collaborative initiatives and programs that involve partnerships between the government, private sector, academia, and other stakeholders to make sure that technologies are used ethically and responsibly. Some of these initiatives are SGInnovate, National Robotics Program, etc. By working together, diverse perspectives are considered for a more balanced and fair approach to digital transformation.

In summary, Singapore's ethical approach combines legal frameworks, AI governance guidelines, and proactive initiatives to ensure responsible and secure digital transformation.

3.4 Tabulated Summary

The comparison of approaches to ethical issues in digital transformation in the respective countries of Estonia and Singapore is summarized below:

Table 1: Comparison of Approaches to ethical issues

Estonia	Singapore
Strategies and Regulations	
Personal Data Protection Act	Personal Data Protection Act (PDPA):
e-Identity	Personal Data Protection Commission (PDPC)
e-Governance Academy	Model AI Governance Framework
Additional Initiatives	
National AI Strategy	National AI Strategy
Public Awareness Campaigns	Public Awareness Campaigns
Citizen Participation in Policy Development	National Digital Identity
Estonian Open Data Portal	Collaborative Initiatives

3.5 Case Study - Ethical and Legal Breaches in Singapore:

In 2018, SingHealth, a major healthcare provider in Singapore, experienced a severe data breach that impacted more than 1.5 million patients. The incident revealed key ethical breaches, highlighting lapses in various areas: The key ethical breaches are Inadequate Cybersecurity Measures, Negligent Handling of Sensitive Patient Data and Inadequate Response to the Data Breach. In response to these ethical breaches, the Personal Data Protection Commission (PDPC) took regulatory action. The PDPC imposed fines of \$250,000 on SingHealth and \$750,000 on Integrated Health Information Systems (IHiS), the technology agency responsible for managing SingHealth's IT systems. These fines were attributed to violations of the Personal Data Protection Act (PDPA) and the insufficient implementation of data protection measures.

This case underscores the importance of maintaining robust cybersecurity measures, handling sensitive data with utmost care, and responding promptly and effectively to data breaches. It serves as a reminder of the ethical responsibilities organizations bear in safeguarding individuals' personal information and the legal consequences they may face when falling short of these obligations.

4. FINDING

4.1 Comparison of Approaches to Addressing Ethical Issues: Similarities

Estonia and Singapore exhibit striking similarities in their approaches to addressing ethical issues in the realm of digital governance. Both nations are committed to ethical digital

governance, focusing on responsible practices and fair practices in technological advancements. And, they have implemented legal frameworks to safeguard individual privacy, encourage public participation, and promote awareness campaigns for digital technologies. After that, they focus on ethical AI development, valuing accountability, transparency, and fairness. In addition, both countries prioritize continuous learning and improvement in the digital landscape, adapting to emerging challenges and technologies, emphasizing the need for flexibility in addressing ethical issues. These similarities highlight the global need for ethical considerations in digital advancement.

4.2 Comparison of Approaches to Addressing Ethical Issues: Differences

Both Estonia and Singapore focus on the same ethical dimensions. There are only different ways implementing on ethical approaches. Estonia prioritizes transparency through digital identity and open data initiatives, allowing citizens to control their information. The government leads this approach, driving digital identity solutions and ethical technology usage. Otherwise, Singapore organizes compliance in the use of digital technologies, aiming to maintain ethical standards. The country balances industry-driven initiatives with compliance, fostering collaboration between government and industry sectors. Businesses are involved in determining ethical technology use, with agencies like A*STAR and PDPC playing key roles in facilitating collaboration and driving initiatives.

This study exposed that Estonia and Singapore have adopted distinct approaches to addressing ethical issues. Both countries share a commitment to ethical digital governance, protecting privacy, and promoting public trust. Estonia's approach is more focused on individual rights and freedoms, Singapore's approach is more focused on mitigating the impact of automation on employment. Addressing ethical issues is crucial for building trust in digital technologies and ensuring their beneficial use for society. By proactively addressing ethical issues, governments, organizations, and individuals can contribute to a more equitable, and inclusive digital future.

5. DISCUSSION

From this study, these are suggestions for government sectors to address ethical issues. Governments should establish robust data protection laws and regulations to ensure a secure digital environment for individuals' data. And, investing in digital literacy programs, research, and education will enhance individuals' ability to navigate the digital landscape more effectively. Consequently, they should encourage public engagement in shaping digital governance policies to promote transparency and trust. Moreover, Global collaboration is crucial for governments to address ethical challenges in digital transformation collectively. Besides, they should strike a balance between innovation and ethics, aiming to reduce the digital divide and ensure fair access to technology for all, while also promoting ethical considerations in their initiatives.

Furthermore, organizations should actively adopt and implement ethical codes of conduct for the development and use of digital technologies to ensure responsible practices. And then, they should implement robust data management practices to safeguard individuals' privacy and security. After that, they should be transparent about their data practices and provide clear privacy policies to build trust with users.

6. CONCLUSION

In the ever-changing world of digital transformation, addressing ethical issues is a continuous and complex process that requires ongoing adaptation and collaboration. It involves understanding present ethical implications and taking proactive measures to mitigate potential risks, ultimately fostering a responsible and sustainable digital future. The unique approaches taken by Estonia and Singapore in their digital journeys offer valuable insights. Estonia emphasizes individual rights and freedoms with a government-led approach, while Singapore focuses on compliance, industry-driven initiatives, and addressing the impact of automation on employment. These diverse approaches underscore the importance of tailoring strategies to specific national contexts. As we navigate the complexities of the digital age, it is clear that ethical considerations are essential for creating a digital landscape that prioritizes individual well-being, safeguards privacy, and promotes inclusive progress. Our country, Myanmar can learn valuable lessons from these experiences as it shapes its own digital future. By embracing ethical principles, fostering transparency, and promoting collaboration, it has the opportunity to innovate ethically, contributing to sustainable development and inclusive progress.

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REFERENCES

1. Abuladze, I., & Manikas, A. (2021). Ethical challenges of digital transformation in Estonia and the transformational role of public administration: A comparative analysis. *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*, 15(1), 1-28.
2. Chang, Y., & Kwek, Y. S. (2022). Digital ethics in the Singaporean context: A critical examination. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 175(4), 933-950.
3. Dutta, D., & Dutta, S. (2021). Digital transformation in Estonia: A case study on the use of e-governance. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 44(14), 1618-1631.
4. Heeks, R., & Rajapakse, J. (2021). Digital transformation in Singapore: A case study on the use of data analytics. *Government Information Quarterly*, 38(1), 59-74.
5. Kannan, K. (2022). Ethical considerations in digital transformation: A case study of Singapore's smart nation initiative. *Journal of Information Systems Research*, 33(1), 24-45.
6. Karunakaran, Sabarish and Rao, Seeram Sambasiva, Comparative Study of E-Governance Implementation in Estonia, Singapore and South Korea (May 24, 2018). SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4451165>
7. Karunakaran, Sabarish and Rao, Seeram Sambasiva, A Comparative Study on E-Governance Data Framework Implementation in Estonia, Republic of Korea & Singapore (June 17, 2023). SSRN Electronic Journal. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4482708>

8. Lee, D.-K., & Lee, T.-C. (2022). Artificial intelligence ethics and the smart nation in Singapore: A critique of the current regulatory framework. *Journal of Technology Law & Policy*, 27(2), 249-271.
9. M. G. (2019, February 28). E-Estonia: The e-government cases of Estonia, Singapore, and Curaçao. *Archives of Business Research*, 7(2). <https://doi.org/10.14738/abr.72.6174>
10. Narayan, V. R. (2022). Data privacy in Estonia: A comparative analysis with Singapore. *The International Journal of Law and Information Technology*, 30(1), 48-71.
11. Sengupta, P. (2022). Ethical considerations in digital transformation: A case study of Singapore's e-government initiatives. *Journal of Information Technology & Politics*, 19(1), 79-94.
12. Subramaniam, M., & Tan, C.-W. (2022). Ethical use of artificial intelligence in Singapore's smart nation initiative: A critical review. *Journal of Information Technology Ethics*, 18(1), 119-142.
13. Tong, Z., & Wang, Y. (2022). Digital transformation in Estonia: A case study on the use of mobile government. *Government Information Quarterly*, 39(2), 100614.
14. Weerakkody, U. (2023). Ethical considerations in the use of big data analytics in Singapore: A case study of the smart nation initiative. *Journal of Information Technology & Politics*, 20(1), 1-16.
15. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/ethical-issues-technology-ways-manage-them-teamleasedigital#>
16. <https://www.dataguidance.com/jurisdiction/estonia>
17. <https://e-estonia.com/solutions/e-identity/id-card/#:~:text=e%2DIdentity,of%20the%20country's%20e%2Dstate.>